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TECHNOLOGY****STATUS OF INTERNATIONALIZATION OF THE COLLEGE OF EDUCATION OF
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DOI: Will get Assigned Shortly.

ABSTRACT

This study ascertained the status of internationalization of the College of Education of Naval State University using the rubric in gauging the level of internationalization of TEIs in the Philippines developed by Balagtas et.al. (2012). It assessed on the status of internationalization in four domains in teacher education and nine domains. The four domains are: 1. Knowledge Creation and Application; 2.) Quality and Excellence; 3.) Culture of Sharing and Service; and 4.) Growth, Efficiency, and Accountability. The nine domains of internationalization in Higher Education Institutions are: 1) Curriculum and Instruction; 2.) Facilities and Support System; 3.) Cooperation and Development Assistance; 4.) Diversity Income Generation; 5.) Research Collaboration; 6.) International and Intercultural Understanding/Networking; 7.) Academic Standards and Quality; 8.) Mobility and Exchanges for Students and Teachers Recruitment.

Findings disclosed that none from the four domains of teacher education and the nine dimensions of internationalization are internationalized to a very great extent and great extent. Nevertheless, the knowledge creation and application and growth, efficiency and accountability are internationalized to a little extent; quality and excellence is internationalized to some extent; yet, not at all internationalized on the culture of sharing and service. For the dimensions of internationalization, the facilities and support system is internationalized to a great extent; the curriculum and instruction is internationalized to some extent. The research collaboration and the diverse income generation are not at all internationalized and the rests of the six dimensions are rated to a little extent.

INTRODUCTION

Globalization poses great challenge in assessing the status of internationalization of the teacher education in the Philippines. Internationalization resolves in the opening up and coming together of business, trade, economic activities between nations which require a greater homogenization of basic political, ideological, cultural and social aspects of life across different countries in the world. (Maringe and Foskette 2010).

Taylor, Rizvi, Lingard and Henry (1997) underscore that internationalization refers to the relationships and transactions between nations rather than to those which transcend national boundaries. Accordingly, it involves cross-country collaborations which illustrate on: international students in undergraduate or postgraduate courses; internationalization of the curriculum and comparative curricula studies; international research conferences; international publications; collaborative and/or comparative cross-country research projects; professional development programs; and international consultancies.

The Naval State University (NSU) which envisions being “a globally competitive state university imbued with positive values contributory to sustainable development and progress” must be ready to embrace this gigantic revolution in education. Thus, the college of NSU assessed on the status of its internationalization to respond on the demands for globalization and the ASEAN integration.

Generally, the study assessed of status of internationalization of the College of Education of Naval State University in four (4) domains in teacher education and nine (9) dimensions of internationalization.

Specifically, it sought to:

1. Find out the level of internationalization in four domains:
 - 1.1. Knowledge creation and application;
 - 1.2. Quality and excellence;
 - 1.3. Culture of sharing and service; and,
 - 1.4. Growth, efficiency, and accountability

2. Determine the level of internationalization in the nine dimensions:
 - 2.1. Curriculum and instruction;
 - 2.2. Facilities and support system;
 - 2.3. Cooperation and development assistance;
 - 2.4. Diversity income generation;
 - 2.5. Research collaboration;
 - 2.6. International and intercultural understanding/networking quality;
 - 2.7. Academic standards and quality;
 - 2.8. Mobility and exchanges for students and teachers;
 - 2.9. International students recruitment

METHODOLOGY

This is a descriptive-evaluative research since its main objective was to assess the status of internationalization of the College of Education of NSU. Using the rubric in gauging the level of internationalization of TEIs in the Philippines developed by Balagtas et.al (2012) and through random sampling the respondents who were chosen to evaluate are the key Officials, faculty and student leaders of the College of Education of Naval State University. A focused group discussion was also conducted to confirm the results of the evaluation survey.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

In the light of the evaluation, analysis and interpretation of data, this study yielded the following results:

1. In the four domains of teacher education: the Knowledge Creation & Application was rated 1.17 which means internationalized to a little extent; Quality and Excellence with the weighted mean of 2.1, internationalized to some extent; Culture Sharing & Service rated 0.66, not at all internationalized; and Growth Efficiency and Accountability obtained 1.33, internationalized to a little extent.
2. For the dimensions of internationalization, the facilities and support system obtained the highest rating of 3 which means internationalized to a high extent; the curriculum and instruction with a weighted mean of 2.1 is internationalized to some extent. The research collaboration and the diverse income generation are not at all internationalized and the rests of the six dimensions are rated to a little extent.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the results the following conclusions were drawn:

1. None from the four domains of teacher education and the nine dimensions of internationalization are internationalized to a very great extent and great extent.
2. The College of Education of NSU exhibited some high status and more on low status in the level of internationalization.

In view of the foregoing conclusions, the following is highly recommended:

1. Formulate a comprehensive development program on the internationalization of the College of Education of NSU.
2. The administration, faculty, staff and students should adhere on the domains and dimensions of internationalization.

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